

Study of tachinid fly parasitization to *Helicoverpa armigera*
hubner on chickpeas crop

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ABSTRACT

The investigations on larval parasitization of gram pod borer, *Helicoverpa armigera* Hubner by tachinid fly, *C. illota* on chickpea were carried out at the Bio- control Laboratory, College of Agriculture, Navsari Agricultural University, Waghai, Dist.- Dangs, Gujarat during Rabi 2020-21, 2021-22 and 2022-23. The The investigations on larval parasitization of gram pod borer, *Helicoverpa armigera* Hubner by tachinid fly, *C. illota* on chickpea were carried out at the Bio- control Laboratory, College of Agriculture, Navsari Agricultural University, Waghai, Dist.- Dangs, Gujarat during Rabi 2020-21, 2021-22 and 2022-23. The total pooled mortality (per cent parasitization by tachinid fly and unknown caused mortality) of *H. armigera* larva was 11.19 per cent during second fortnight of February with 4.40 ± 5.77 per cent mean total mortality. Pooled maximum parasitization by tachinid fly, *C. illota* was 2.38 per cent observed during first fortnight of February with mean 0.87 ± 1.02 per cent.

Key words: Gram pod borer, *Helicoverpa*, larval parasitization, tachinid fly

1. INTRODUCTION

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) forms an integral part of vegetarian diet as a protein substitute in the Indian sub-continent. It has an important place in the diet of Indian people because it gives comparatively more protein, vitamins and minerals than any other food grains. It has 21.1% protein, 6.15% carbohydrate and 4.5% fat (Haq et al., 2007; Pittaway et al., 2008). Besides being a very rich source of protein, it also maintains soil fertility through biological nitrogen fixation. In present scenario there is tremendous scope for increasing the productivity of gram by reducing the production losses caused by serious pests. The pests and extent of losses differs among various agro-ecological zones.

Gram is severely affected by half a dozen major pests. On an average 30-80% crop losses occur in pulses due to ravages of insect-pests. Single larva of the gram pod borer destroys 30-40 pods before its maturity. Annual damage due to gram pod borer alone is around 150-200 millions (Bohria et al., 2011).

Gram pod borer are being attacked by number of parasitoids, predators and entomopathogens and playing critical role in the natural regulation of pest population and these potent bioagents could be exploited for the management of Gram pod borer. In India, altogether 100 parasitoids of *H. armigera* have been reported (Nikam and Gaikwad, 1989). Among these, tachinid fly is an important (Srinivas and Jayraj, 1989, Singh et al., 1991). *Carcelia illota* (Curran) is a larval ex-pupal parasitoid of *H. armigera* (Manjunath et al., 1989). So the present study was carried out to know the status of tachinid fly parasitism on chickpea pod borer.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out at Bio-control Laboratory, College of Agriculture, Navsari Agricultural University, Waghai, Dist. - Dangs, Gujarat during Rabi 2020-21, 2021-22 and 2022-23. To know the parasitization of chickpea pod borer larvae under field conditions, available

stages of chickpea pod borer larvae were collected from farmer's field at fortnightly interval irrespective of variety and brought to laboratory for the further rearing and assessment of parasitization. Collected larvae were kept individually in plastic vials measuring 55 x 25 mm in the laboratory at room temperature for rearing them up to adult stage. Records on number of larvae collected in each collection were maintained. These larvae were provided fresh twigs of chickpea daily in the morning in the vial. Observations on moulting and death of larvae. Emergence of immature/adults of parasitoid, pupation, death in pupal stage and adult moth emergence were also recorded daily in the morning. The emerged parasitoid was collected separately to avoid assimilation of species. The date, place and stage of the host insect were recorded. The collected natural enemies of gram pod borer were preserved for further studies. The taxonomic study of collected specimens was studied under the microscope. The important taxonomic characters of the collected specimens were identified by using dichotomous keys, visual observation and confirmed with the help of published literature. The unidentified specimens were sent to respective taxonomist for identification. The data thus recorded on larvae and pupae were tabulated and per cent parasitization was worked out by using following formula

$$\text{Parasitization \%} = \frac{\text{No. of parasitoid emerged}}{\text{No. of larvae/pupae reared}} \times 100$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Total mortality

2020-21

The result presented in Table 1 revealed that maximum total mortality (per cent parasitization by tachinid fly and unknown caused mortality) of *H. armigera* larva was 18.18 per cent during second fortnight of February with 7.46 ± 5.48 per cent mean mortality.

2021-22

The result presented in Table 2 revealed that maximum total mortality of *H. armigera* larva was 6.66 per cent during second fortnight of December with 2.77 ± 2.52 per cent mean total mortality.

2022-23

The result presented in Table 3 revealed that maximum total mortality of *H. armigera* larva was 15.38 per cent during second fortnight of February with 4.40 ± 5.77 per cent mean total mortality. Pooled data of three year presented in Table 4 revealed that maximum total mortality of *H. armigera* larva was 11.19 per cent during second fortnight of February with 4.40 ± 5.77 per cent mean total mortality.

3.2 Parasitization by Tachinid fly, *Carcelia illota* (Curran)

2020-21

Table 1: Larval parasitization of gram pod borer, *H. armigera* during 2020-2021

Month	Fortnight	No. of larvae collected	No. of larvae dead	Total per cent mortality	Per cent larvae parasitized by Tachinid fly	Mortality by unknown cause
Dec.	I	33.00	2.00	6.06	0.00	6.06
	II	120.0	7.00	5.83	0.00	5.83
Jan.	I	286.0	7.00	2.45	0.00	2.45
	II	180.0	13.00	7.22	1.66	5.55
Feb.	I	178.0	9.00	5.05	1.13	3.92
	II	22.00	4.00	18.18	4.54	13.64
	Min.	22.00	2.00	2.45	0.00	2.45
	Max.	286.0	13.00	18.18	4.54	13.64
	Mean \pm SD	136.50 ± 100.06	7.00 ± 3.84	7.46 ± 5.48	1.22 ± 1.77	6.24 ± 3.87

Table 2: Larval parasitization of gram pod borer, *H. armigera* during 2021-2022

Month	Fortnight	No. of larvae collected	No. of larvae dead	Total per cent mortality	Per cent larvae parasitized by Tachinid fly	Mortality by unknown cause
Dec.	I	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	II	15.00	1.00	6.66	0.00	6.66
Jan.	I	211.00	6.00	2.84	0.00	2.84
	II	540.00	19.00	3.52	0.74	2.78
Feb.	I	83.00	3.00	3.61	3.61	0.00
	II	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Min.	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Max.	540.00	19.00	6.66	3.61	6.66
	Mean \pm SD	141.50 ± 211.24	4.83 ± 7.30	2.77 ± 2.52	0.73 ± 1.45	2.04 ± 2.64

Table 3: Larval parasitization of gram pod borer, *H. armigera* during 2022-2023

Month	Fortnight	No. of larvae collected	No. of larvae dead	Total per cent mortality	Per cent larvae parasitized by Tachinid fly	Mortality by unknown cause
Dec.	I	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	II	7.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Jan.	I	65.00	2.00	3.08	0.00	0.00
	II	125.00	7.00	5.60	1.60	4.00
Feb.	I	42.00	1.00	2.38	2.38	0.00
	II	13.00	2.00	15.38	0.00	15.38
Min.		0.00			0.00	
Max.		125.00			0.00	
Mean ± SD		42.00 ± 47.43	2.00 ± 2.60	4.40 ± 5.77	0.66 ± 1.06	3.23 ± 6.16

Table 4: Larval parasitization of gram pod borer, *H. armigera* during 2020-21 to 2022-23 (Pooled)

Month	Fortnight	No. of larvae collected	No. of larvae dead	Total per cent mortality	Per cent larvae parasitized by Tachinid fly	Mortality by unknown cause
Dec.	I	11.00	0.67	2.02	0.00	2.02
	II	47.33	2.67	4.16	0.00	4.16
Jan.	I	187.33	5.00	2.79	0.00	1.76
	II	281.67	13.00	5.45	1.33	4.11
Feb.	I	101.00	4.33	3.68	2.38	1.31
	II	11.67	2.00	11.19	1.51	9.67
Min.		11.00	0.67	2.02	0.00	2.02
Max.		281.67	13.00	11.19	2.38	9.67
Mean ± SD		106.67 ± 108.50	4.61 ± 4.39	4.88 ± 3.30	0.87 ± 1.02	3.83 ± 3.10

2022-23

The result presented in Table 3 revealed that, gram pod borer larvae were naturally parasitized by tachinid fly, *C. illota*. Maximum parasitization 2.38 per cent was observed during first fortnight of February with mean 0.66 ± 1.06 per cent.

Pooled data of three year presented in Table 4 revealed that, gram pod borer larvae were naturally parasitized by tachinid fly, *C. illota*. Maximum parasitization 2.38 per cent was observed during first fortnight of February with mean 0.87 ± 1.02 per cent.

The above finding also supported by extent of parasitization of *H. armigera* larvae due to tachinid fly ranged between 0 to 23.0 per cent during 2011-12 and 6.67 to 33.33 per cent during

2012-13 (Saurabh Singh et al., 2014). Bisane et al., 2008 reported that 0 to 25 per cent parasitization of *H. armigera* larvae due to tachinid fly. Borkar and Sarode, 2013 stated that tachinid fly were found effective parasitoid of *H. armigera*.

4. CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that gram pod borer larvae were naturally parasitized by tachinid fly, *C. illota* in the range of 0.74 to 4.54 per cent during second fortnight of January to second fortnight of February on chickpea crop. This study is helpful for the development of management practices of gram pod borer in chickpea crop.

5. DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

We agree to make available the data when necessary.

6. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

We declare that, there is no potential conflict of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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